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NOD2 controls expression of genes important for sex determination.

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We describe an apparently essential role for NOD2 in control of expression of genes important for sex determination. Gene products that fell under the purvey of NOD2 regulation as part of a designed module in mammalian sex determination included those functioning in Mullerian duct regression. The data indicated Nod2 functions in speciation or in physiologic functions or processes associated with higher-level anatomic organization or physiologic processes that reflect importance or relevance of evolution or selection pressure in human genetics.

1 **Results**

2
3 We found a wide network of factors important for Mullerian duct regression and sex determination to get NOD2 transcriptional targets.

4 Amh
5 Amhr
6 Amhr2
7 Sox9
8 Sox8
9 Sry
10 Dmrt1
11 Wnt4
12 Wnt7a
13 Nr5a1 (sf1)
14 Foxl2
15 Bmpr1a

- 16
17 1. NOD2 activates DMRT1.
18 Mutant NOD2 is defective in DMRT activation.
- 19 2. NOD2 activates Sox9.
20 Activation of Sox9 by mutant NOD2 is very weak
- 21 3. NOD2 moderately represses SRY expression.
22 Mutant NOD2 instead very weakly activates SRY expression.

23 Differences in Sox8/Sox9 homeobox expression between wild-type and mutant NOD2.

- 24 4. In the presence of MDP, activation of Sox9 and DMRT1 by wild-type NOD2 is completely lost.
- 25 5. Mutant NOD2 fails to repress Sox9 and DMRT1 in response to MDP pattern recognition.
- 26 6. AMHR2 activation by MDP is significantly enhanced by mutation of NOD2.
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Methods

Gse22611
Wild-type NOD2 in embryonic cells
NOD2 L1007P in embryonic cells

Wild-type NOD2 in embryonic cells +MDP
NOD2 L1007P in embryonic cells +MDP

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Supplemental Data

- 1. NLRP7, 8, 9, 10 and 11 co- regulate genes important for sex determination in mammals
- 2. Deletion of NLRP7 results in induction of AMH, and loss of Fosl1 and Wnt4 expression